

negative values at 45° than at 25° or 35°. It is also observed that ΔH is positive in all cases which suggests that there exists steric strain around the metal ion in the chelates due to fused rings. The positive values of ΔS for all the chelates indicate that entropy term is favourable for their formation.

The data were analysed in terms of Harned's¹⁰ relation between $\log K^H$ and temperature $[(pK_m^H - ct^2) = -2c\theta t + (pK_m^H - c\theta^2)]$. A plot of $(pK_m^H - ct^2)$ vs t must be linear and this was found true in the present case. The values of θ° and pK_m^H for HFB were found 211° and 3.550 respectively. ΔH values as calculated from Harned's equation were found 7.914, 7.794 and 7.681 at 25°, 35° and 45° respectively.

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Separation and Determination of Zirconium with N-Benzoyl-*o*-Tolyl Hydroxylamine

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N-BENZOYL-*O*-TOLYL hydroxylamine which was used for the precipitation and determination of niobium and tantalum by Majumdar and Pal¹ has later been used as a reagent in gravimetric and spectrophotometric determination of a variety of metals²⁻³.

Experimental

Reagent :

N-benzoyl-*o*-tolyl hydroxylamine was prepared by the procedure given by Pal⁴. The product was recrystallised from ethanol.

Standard Solution :

A standard solution of zirconium was prepared from Johnson & Mathey 'Specpure' zirconium oxychloride. The solution of zirconium was standardised gravimetrically as oxide by cupferron⁵ and N-benzoyl phenyl hydroxylamine⁶⁻⁷.

An Elico Model L 1-10 pH-meter was used for all pH measurements.

Procedure :

An aliquot of standard zirconium solution was diluted to 100 ml, pH was adjusted between 0.4-2.2 with dilute ammonia or mineral acid and the solution warmed. The reagent in ethanol and water mixture (1 : 1) was then added to the solution very slowly with thorough stirring after each addition, when a milky white precipitate appeared, which was digested for 20-25 minutes on the boiling water bath. The solution was then cooled to room temperature and filtered through a Whatman No. 42 filter paper, washed with 0.1% reagent solution and ignited to oxide in a platinum crucible.

pH effect :

The precipitate of zirconium was found to be quantitative between pH 0.4 to 2.2; at higher pH zirconium precipitate assumed colloidal form and at higher acid concentrations the precipitate dissolved on warming. The determination of zirconium by direct weighing was not possible since the complex was contaminated with the reagent.

Separation of foreign ions :

Solution containing known amounts of different foreign ions with zirconium were mixed with a 5% (w/v) tartaric acid solution. The amount of tartaric acid was 10-15 times the total ions. Addition of reagent (20 times the amount of zirconium) and the adjustment of pH were made according to the general procedure. The ions Ca²⁺(100 mg), Mg²⁺(100 mg), Ba²⁺(100 mg), Sr²⁺(100 mg), Be²⁺(50 mg), Al³⁺(100 mg), Ni²⁺(80 mg), Co²⁺(100 mg), Cu²⁺(100 mg), Zn²⁺(100 mg), Cd²⁺(100 mg), As³⁺(100 mg), Sn²⁺(80 mg), Hg²⁺(80 mg), UO₂²⁺(60 mg), Th⁴⁺(60 mg), Mn²⁺(100 mg), Cr³⁺(100 mg), Bi³⁺(100 mg), Ce³⁺(60 mg), Br⁻(50 mg), I⁻(50 mg) and BO₃³⁻(50 mg) did not interfere. Only Ti(IV), V(V), Ce(IV), Fe(III), Mo(IV), WO₄²⁻, Nb⁵⁺, Ta⁵⁺ and Hf(IV) interfered. To remove their interfering effect iron was masked by thioglycollic acid;

titanium, vanadium and cerium by hydrogen peroxide. Molybdenum, tungsten, niobium and tantalum were removed by keeping the acid concentration high and by hot filtration when zirconium alone remained in solution. After filtration, zirconium was precipitated in the usual way at the required pH. The interference of hafnium could not however be removed.

Standard Deviation :

The standard deviation for sixteen determinations of zirconium (containing 8.8 mg of the metal oxide) with N-phenyl-o-tolyl hydroxylamine was ± 0.012 .

Metal ion Added	ZrO ₂ Taken (mg)	ZrO ₂ Found (mg)	Relative mean error (%)	Metal ion Added	ZrO ₂ Taken (mg)	ZrO ₂ Found (mg)	Relative mean error (%)
Fe(II)				WO ₅ ⁺			
80 mg	8.80	8.80	+0.057	60 mg	8.80	8.80	± 0
80 mg	8.80	8.81		60 mg	8.80	8.80	
Ti(IV)				Nb ⁵⁺			
100 mg	8.80	8.79	-0.171	50 mg	8.80	8.81	+0.171
100 mg	8.80	8.78		50 mg	8.80	8.82	
Ce(IV)				Ta ⁵⁺			
50 mg	8.80	8.80	+0.057	10 mg	8.80	8.78	-0.057
50 mg	8.80	8.81		10 mg	8.80	8.81	
MoO ₄ ²⁻				VO ₅ ⁻			
100 mg	8.80	8.78	-0.171	60 mg	8.80	8.81	+0.057
100 mg	8.80	8.79		60 mg	8.80	8.80	

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Studies on EGTA Complexes of VO₂⁺ by Spectrophotometry

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EDTA (H₄Y) forms a complex compound VO₂Y⁻³ with pentavalent vanadium with stability constant, log K=18.05 in 0.1M NaClO₄ medium. At pH values below about 3.5 the species VO₂HY⁻² is

formed and the acidic dissociation constant of this compound is $pK_a = 3.60^1$. The equilibrium constant for the reaction $VO_2^+ + Y^{4-} = VO_2Y^{-3}$ in 0.1M KCl medium was also determined by other authors² to be log K=15.55. Nothing is known about the complex formed by pentavalent vanadium with ethylene glycol bis(aminoethyl ether)-N,N,N',N'-tetraacetic acid (EGTA or H₄L), a complexing agent analogous to EDTA.

Experimental

EGTA was obtained from Pfaltz and Bauer, Inc. and it was purified by crystallisation from hot water. Ammonium vanadate was E. Merck AG grade. All spectrophotometric studies were made by using an EC spectrophotometer model GS 865A and all pH measurements were made by using an EC expanded scale pH meter model pH 821A.

To a known volume of an ammonium vanadate solution was added a known solution of disodium salt of EGTA. The pH of this mixture was adjusted with dilute HClO₄ or NaOH solution. The whole mixture was then brought to a known volume in a measuring flask while the ionic strength was kept at approximately 0.1M by addition of NaClO₄ solution. The temperature was Ca. 22°. The pH of each of these solutions was measured in the pH meter with an agaragar-KCl salt bridge. Next, the absorbance of the same solution was measured in the spectrophotometer. All the measurements were carried out at 22°.

After a study was made with pH versus molar absorbance of the solution at 340 nm in the whole pH range (2 to 13), the data was plotted in Fig. 1. Next, in the pH range where the formation of the

Fig. 1. Molar absorbance of vanadium at 340 nm in an excess of EGTA as a function of pH + C_V = 2 × 10⁻³ M, C_{EGTA} = 1 × 10⁻² M.

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